

Universal Learning

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Abstract

While machine learning has been quite successful in many different domains, we are still quite far from machines that can learn at the level of humans in disparate domains. Can there be a succinct specification that can place us much closer to human-level learning when achieved? We suggest one such specification: *universal learning*.

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Introduction

While machine learning has been quite successful in many different domains, we are still quite far from machines that can learn at the level of humans in disparate domains [1, 2, 3]. Consider these quite different problems:

- P₁** There is no system that can read, for example, an academic paper on machine learning and accurately construct from scratch the system described in the paper or suggest improvements to the system in the paper.
- P₂** Learning systems for one problem ρ fare abysmally when faced with a slightly different problem $\rho + \delta$ or the same problem in a different modality ρ^m . For example, there is no evidence to suggest AlphaGo, without significant modification, will fare well in a slightly different version of Go (e.g. a version of Go in which exactly one randomly chosen rule is invalid in each round), or a Go game played through ambiguous natural language in which states of the game are conveyed to the players through clues in natural language.
- P₃** More practically, deploying and improving a learning system takes quite a lot of domain and machine learning expertise.
- P₄** A child steals from a friend and is reprimanded verbally. The child promptly learns that it is wrong to steal.

Can we solve problems similar to the above with *one* simple specification of a learning system (rather than haphazardly tie together several disparate formalisms)? We propose one such specification below that we term universal learning. This should be viewed as a necessary condition rather than a sufficient one.

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Among the different tasks that humans learn, we have at the higher end of the learning spectrum, learning in mathematical

and formal domains such as **P₁** above. As a first approximation, this suggests that if machines can learn at the level of humans computationally hard functions in a manner similar to that of humans, we could be much closer to solving problems similar to the ones described above (as mentioned above, a necessary rather than a sufficient condition).

Let us suppose we have a set of functions **H** such that:

1. the universal function u (capable of computing any computable function, or a universal Turing machine) is Turing reducible to any function $h \in \mathbf{H}$.
2. For each $h \in \mathbf{H}$, there is a human that has *real-learned* the function h as defined by the sense of real-learning defined in [1].

Many economically important functions belong to this set. For example, the function v which outputs 1 if a machine (or program) m adheres to a set of conditions Φ and 0 otherwise belongs to **H** (see [4]).

Let n be the total number of function input/output examples used by humans in real-learning definitions for **H** and m be a measure of the complexity and number of definitions used in real-learning members of **H**.

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A system is said to be capable of **universal learning** if it can produce definitions for all $h \in \mathbf{H}$ from $\mathcal{O}(n)$ examples and $\mathcal{O}(m)$ definitions.

References

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